

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15235738>

THE IDEOLOGICAL VIEWS OF THE JADIDS ARE TRANSFORMING INTO PRACTICAL LIFE IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION.

This article focuses on the activities of the Jadids and their views on the issues of educating a harmoniously developed generation, on the fact that the Jadids of Turkestan promoted the idea of freeing the people from backwardness and religious prejudice, creating an independent state where free thinking prevails, spreading enlightenment to the people, and achieving national autonomy. At the same time, it is said that the reforms being carried out today in New Uzbekistan coincide with the ideological views of the Jadids, and the ideas they conceived are becoming a practical process.

Keywords: *Jadid, ideological processes, enlightenment, Jadid method, national uprising, press, national idea, reforms being implemented in "New Uzbekistan" and practical expression of "Jadids" ideas.*

ENTRANCE.

Changes in each society manifest themselves based on the historical conditions of its time. Historical figures, especially the intelligentsia, played a significant role in these changes, and each of them put forward their own progressive ideas. Intellectuals try to find ways to solve socio-economic problems in society. A similar process occurred in the second half of the 19th century in Crimea, Transcaucasia, Turkestan,

the Bukhara Emirate, which became a protectorate, and the Khiva Khanate, which were part of the Russian Empire. In the second half of the 19th century, intellectuals under colonial oppression began actions aimed at enlightening their peoples and raising their level of development. The term "Jadid" translated from Arabic means "New."

This term first appeared among the Turkic peoples during the reign of the Ottoman Turkish ruler Sultan Selim III. Abubakr Ratib Efendi, who was sent as an ambassador to the Austrian state, in his letters to the sultan, explains to the sultan that the system of administration he saw there is "Nizami jadid." The positive aspect of this system was that the development of society determined the progress of the country, determined the level of the state in political activity. "Nizami jadid" envisioned the Europeanization of the administrative system, in a broad sense, the modernization of science, education, industry, and agriculture.

At the end of the 19th century, the enormous cultural-educational, socio-political changes taking place in world civilization, new relations, in one way or another, began to penetrate the Turkestan region. The Jadids, under the influence of the "Ghanch (Young) Turks" organizations in the Ottoman Turkish state, formed a Jadid organization in the Turkestan region under the names "Young Bukharans," "Young Khivans," and "Young Turkestanis."

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

If the initial activity of the Jadid movement began in school and education, then in the period of its subsequent activity it moved to the sphere of press, art, and politics. Ismail Gasprinsky (1851-1914) founded the Jadid movement in Russia and its colonies. In 1884, he opened the first "usuli jadid" (new method) school in Bakhchisaray, Crimea. Having deeply mastered religious and secular knowledge, he became closely acquainted with world development, studied several foreign languages and the culture of different peoples. Ismail Gasprinsky's greatest contribution was to introduce and bring closer to each other the Turkic peoples living within the borders of Russia, but who, due to the circumstances of the time, had become distant and estranged from each other.

Jadidism, which entered the sphere of social life of Turkestan as a cultural and educational movement and set itself the goal of reforming the old school, was formed as a broad social movement. By the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries, the national awakening, reflecting the views of the most progressive thinkers of society, manifested itself as a certain ideology, primarily in the Enlightenment. The Jadids were determined to form a social and national consciousness of the entire Turkestan people to initially fight against colonial rule. They believed that the main path to liberating the region from backwardness and oppression lay primarily in the cultural and educational direction, and by opening new-method schools, they sought to redirect the people to a new socio-cultural course. To awaken the nation and encourage its progress, the Jadid enlighteners began by establishing a newspaper. Through printed publications such as "Tarjimon," "Oyina," "Taraqqiy," "Sadoyi Turkiston," "Sadoyi Farg'ona," "Najot," "Hurriyat," "Al-isloh," they strived to bring life-giving ideas such as national independence, freedom, and enlightenment to the people. If we pay attention to the views of the Jadid enlighteners, most of them paid serious attention to the proper organization of upbringing in the family. As the great Jadid enlightener Abdurauf Fitrat noted: "Parents should seriously engage in the upbringing of their child, but parents engaged in child-rearing must, first of all, have certain knowledge about the upbringing of their child, both of them must perfectly fulfill their duties, their parental duty, so that they raise the child physically, mentally, and morally, and bring them to life with strong, intelligent, and good morals".

The above-mentioned ideas of our Jadid ancestors are becoming practical results in New Uzbekistan under the leadership of our respected President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. The Head of State announced his decision to award the Order "For Great Services" to the Jadids Abdulla Avloni, Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, and Munavvarkori Abdurashidkhanov, who were executed by the Soviets at the celebration on October 1st, Teacher and Mentor Day. He gave instructions to create a "Collection of Jadids" dedicated to the memory of our patriotic Jadids, especially mentioning the names of Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, Munavvar qori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulla

Qodiriy, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Abdulla Avloniy, Is'hoqxon To'ra, and G'ulom Zafariy, and ensured the implementation of the resolution in a short time.

RESULT.

In this process, drawing conclusions from the historical past of our country, under the leadership of our esteemed President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, our reforms aimed at building a just, free, and prosperous society, a people's state, and a prosperous life in New Uzbekistan are in harmony with the noble ideas and programs of our Jadid forefathers. The ideological-political, socio-educational, and legal-moral views put forward by our great enlightened ancestors, along with establishing the principles of tolerance and harmony between different nations and ethnic groups, and their aspirations to protect national interests, serve as a true example for all of us, especially our youth, in today's complex times.

Currently, the widespread promotion of innovative and creative achievements and a worthy response to the intensifying competition on a global scale through the spiritual heritage left by our ancestors is becoming a priority in our daily activities as a strategic task. Therefore, the spiritual heritage created by our ancestors fills us, the descendants, with pride in the upbringing of the younger generation and means that love for the Motherland in the hearts of people is the highest value. The invaluable didactic heritage created by our ancestors serves as an important factor in the education and upbringing of youth. Today, the harmonization of the educational methods created by them with advanced foreign experience and their effective use in the educational process, in turn, allows achieving the expected effectiveness in the educational process.

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